

Figure S1. The growth curves of pNirS, pEV and PAO1 strains.

Figure S2. The relative expression levels of *nirS* gene in pNirS and pEV strains when biofilms formed in chronic wound model. The data indicate the relative expression levels in biofilms compared to planktonic cells. Bars are representative of three biological replicates. Three technical replicates were performed and averaged for each biological replicate. Error bars represent standard deviation from three biological replicates. *P* values that are significantly different by T-test are indicated by asterisks as follows: *, *P* < 0.05; **, *P* < 0.01; ***, *P* < 0.001. Raw data is available in **Table S5**.

PAO1

pNirS

pEV

Figure S3. Elevated intracellular NO level increases swimming motility of *P. aeruginosa* PAO1.

Figure S4. *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 biofilm developed in head and tail of *C. elegans* when infected for 4 h.

Figure S5. Pyocyanin production (OD_{695}) was measured in pNirS and pEV strains. Three technical replicates were performed and averaged for each biological replicate. Error bars represent standard deviation from three biological replicates. *P* values that are significantly different by T-test are indicated by asterisks as follows: *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$; ***, $P < 0.001$.

Table S1 The raw data respond to Figure 2

mean	PAO1	pNirS	pEV	P value(pNirS_vs_pEV)
planktonic	147.2	155.9	149.2	0.745
biofilm-24 h	135.2	196.0	123.3	0.004
biofilm-48 h	52.4	72.7	22.7	0.039
biofilm-72 h	67.5	66.4	134.2	0.054

SD	PAO1	pNirS	pEV
planktonic	9.45	29.53	16.06
biofilm-24 h	3.32	6.21	2.99
biofilm-48 h	14.03	16.67	12.99
biofilm-72 h	11.31	22.18	6.68

Table S2 Raw data respond to Figure 3.

Mean_24 h	pNirS	pEV	P value
lasI	-0.23	1.87	0.0009
lasR	-1.02	-0.80	0.8691
rhII	0.08	1.60	0.0036
rhIR	0.20	0.18	0.9755
pslA	0.41	1.11	0.0618
pelC	1.81	2.79	0.0193
pqsR	0.20	2.13	0.0060
phzM	-1.54	8.49	0.0024

SD_24 h	pNirS	pEV
lasI	0.15	0.18
lasR	0.16	1.60
rhII	0.25	0.17
rhIR	0.12	0.87
pslA	0.18	0.30
pelC	0.40	0.07
pqsR	0.03	0.37
phzM	0.86	1.26

Mean_48 h	pNirS	pEV	P value
lasI	2.38	2.20	0.621
lasR	0.53	0.65	0.738
rhII	2.73	2.38	0.258
rhIR	2.18	2.63	0.120
pslA	4.06	2.22	0.241
pelC	3.47	3.74	0.732
pqsR	2.42	1.99	0.170
phzM	-0.30	7.26	0.005

SD_48 h	pNirS	pEV
lasI	0.40	0.18
lasR	0.45	0.07
rhII	0.13	0.29
rhIR	0.23	0.09
pslA	0.16	1.57
pelC	0.63	0.75
pqsR	0.28	0.08
phzM	0.06	0.77

Mean_72 h	pNirS	pEV	P value
lasI	1.91	2.26	0.052
lasR	-1.15	-0.56	0.656
rhII	1.59	1.79	0.305
rhIR	1.09	1.57	0.435
pslA	2.53	2.25	0.555
pelC	3.23	4.13	0.009
pqsR	2.51	2.93	0.141
phzM	-0.47	3.37	0.011

SD_72 h	pNirS	pEV
lasI	0.13	0.18
lasR	0.12	1.60
rhII	0.24	0.17
rhIR	0.40	0.87
pslA	0.67	0.30
pelC	0.32	0.07
pqsR	0.13	0.37
phzM	0.78	1.26

Table S3 Raw data respond to Figure 6.

Time (day)	pNirS	pEV	PAO1	OP50
0	180	180	184	178
1	180	180	184	178
2	168	136	146	175
3	142	125	101	175
4	127	109	88	166
5	106	74	83	153
survival ratio	58.89%	41.11%	45.11%	85.96%

Table S4 Statistical data of pNirS compared to pEV respond to Figure 6.

Comparison of Survival Curves		
Log-rank (Mantel-Cox) test		
Chi square	6.712	
df	1	
P value	0.0096	
P value summary	**	
Are the survival curves sig different?	Yes	
Gehan-Breslow-Wilcoxon test		
Chi square	9.83	
df	1	
P value	0.0017	
P value summary	**	
Are the survival curves sig different?	Yes	
Median survival		
Data Set-A	5	
Data Set-B	4	
Ratio (and its reciprocal)	1.25	0.8
95% CI of ratio	0.9565 to 1.634	0.6121 to 1.046
Hazard Ratio (Mantel-Haenszel)	A/B	B/A
Ratio (and its reciprocal)	0.678	1.475
95% CI of ratio	0.5053 to 0.9097	1.099 to 1.979
Hazard Ratio (logrank)	A/B	B/A
Ratio (and its reciprocal)	0.7258	1.378
95% CI of ratio	0.5554 to 0.9484	1.054 to 1.800

Table S5 Raw data respond to Figure S2.

$2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$			
Time	pNirS	pEV	<i>P</i> value
24 h	0.67	0.52	0.0014893
48 h	1.63	0.43	7.093E-06
72 h	0.63	0.45	8.125E-06

SD		
Time	pNirS	pEV
24 h	0.036	0.026
48 h	0.024	0.017
72 h	0.015	0.008